

2'-Hydroxyacetophenonebenzoylhydrazone as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(III)

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2'-Hydroxyacetophenonebenzoylhydrazone (HABH) forms a light red 1 : 2 (V : HABH) complex with V^{III} species at 50–60° in 0.12–0.20 M CH₃COOH medium which is extracted into benzene and has λ_{\max} at 465 nm. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and standard deviation are $1.05 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $0.0049 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$ and ± 0.0006 respectively, at 465 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0–1.5 $\mu\text{g V ml}^{-1}$. Large number of elements do not interfere. The method can be used to determine vanadium in a wide variety of synthetic and technical samples including alloyed steel and reverberatory flue dust.

Much of the work on spectrophotometric determination of vanadium has been carried out on pentavalent state¹ of the metal ion, whereas the lower valence states (IV,III,II) have received little attention for their lack of stability due to rapid oxidation. Keeping this fact in view, an attempt has been made to study complex formation and extraction behaviour of V^{III} for its determination with 2'-hydroxyacetophenonebenzoylhydrazone (HABH) in acidic medium which not only improves the sensitivity of the system as compared to V^V-HABH ($\epsilon = 8.93 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) but also makes it more selective.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(III) obtained by sodium dithionite reduction of vanadium(V)² gave a light red complex in neutral to weakly acidic media which was quantitatively extracted into benzene. In strong acids like HCl, H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄, fading of the colour was observed, whereas in acetic acid medium colour was found to be highly stable. The absorption spectrum of the complex in benzene indicated λ_{\max} at 465 nm where the reagent blank showed negligible absorbance.

Many water-immiscible solvents such as isobutyl methyl ketone, amyl alcohol, n-butyl acetate, dichloromethane, dichloroethane and toluene extracted the complex from 60–95% in that order. Though chloroform and benzene gave quantitative extraction, the colour was found to be less stable (only for 5 min) in chloroform whereas benzene showed much higher stability (more than 5 days) and hence was preferred.

The optimum values of various parameters found for 0–15 $\mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}$ in 10 ml aqueous solution giving maximum and constant absorbance were : 190–325 mg of sodium dithionite, 0.12–0.20 M CH₃COOH, 0.4–1.0 ml of 0.1% HABH solution in acetone, heating at 50–60° for 30 s before extraction and equilibrating once between 30 s–4

min with an equal volume of benzene. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 0–1.5 $\mu\text{g V ml}^{-1}$. However, the optimum range of determination of vanadium as evaluated from Ringbom plot was calculated to be 0.5–1.58 ppm. The molar extinction coefficient and Sandell's sensitivity were $1.05 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0049 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The method was highly reproducible with a standard deviation of ± 0.0006 absorbance unit in ten replicate analyses for 1 $\mu\text{g V ml}^{-1}$ in pure solutions. The 1 : 2 composition of V^{III}-HABH complex in the extracted species was determined by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper at different wavelengths and the same was confirmed by mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods.

Table 1. Determination of V in synthetic and real samples

Sl. no.	Composition (mg)	V added μg	V found* μg
1.	Fe(0.014), Co(0.019) ^a	5	4.9
2.	Fe(0.3), Co(0.3), Mn(0.002) ^b	10	10.0
3.	Fe(1.2), Cr(0.16), Co(0.01) ^c	10	10.2
4.	Ni(0.03), Pt(0.01), Pd(0.003) ^d	5	5.0
5.	Th(1), Cu(1), Mg(2)	15	15.3
6.	U(0.5), Pt(0.01), Se(1)	5	5.3
7.	Mo(0.005), W(0.05), Re(0.01), Mn(2)	5	5.0
8.	Ta(0.05), Cr(0.1), Nb(0.01)	10	10.2
9.	Ti(1), U(0.5), Th(1), Ir(0.05)	5	5.2
10.	High speed steel super rapid extra 500 ^e (200)	1% ^f	0.965%
11.	Reverberatory flue dust ^e (100)	10	10.2

*Average of duplicate analyses.

^{a-d}Compositions analogous to vicalloy, permendur, crocar and palau, respectively. ^eIn presence of 20 mg ascorbic acid. ^fCertified value.

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the proposed procedure containing 10 $\mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}$, the ions/complexing agents added as their sodium or potassium salts in 10 ml aqueous phase (mg amounts in parentheses) such as chloride, thiocyanate (100 each); bromide, iodide (70 each), nitrate (50); sulphate (40); sulphite, thiourea (30

Table 2. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous condition	Solvent, λ_{\max} nm	Sandell's sensitivity, $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ Molar absorptivity, $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Interfering metal ions
1.	V ^V , pH 3.5–4.5 hydrazone compounds ^a	– 525	0.0033, 1.54×10^4	Fe ^{II,III} , Co ^{II} , Pd ^{II}
2.	V ^V , 0.1–0.6 M CH ₃ COOH, heating at 40–55°, 0.1% 2',4'-dihydroxyacetophenone-benzoylhydrazone in ethanol ^a	Dichloroethane, 370–373	0.004, 1.25×10^4	Ti ^{IV}
3.	V ^V , 1 M H ₂ SO ₄ , 0.1% ferron ^a	Tribenzylamine-chloroform, 390	0.006, 8.46×10^3	Fe ^{III} , Mo ^{VI} , Cu ^{II}
4.	V ^V , pH 3.5–4.5 ^b	0.1% oxine in chloroform, 550	0.016, 3.18×10^3	Mo ^{VI} , U ^{VI} , W ^{VI} , Ti ^{IV} , Bi ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{III}
5.	V ^V , 0.5 M Na ₂ WO ₄ , 2H ₂ O, PO ₄ ³⁻ , 0.25 M H ₂ SO ₄ , HNO ₃ , HCl ^b	n-Butanol, 400	0.023, 2.21×10^3	Cr ^{VI} , Mo ^{VI} , Bi ^{III,V} , Sb ^{III,V} , Ti ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Sn ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II}
6.	V ^V , pH 1.9–2.8, 0.1% benzoylphenyl hydroxylamine ^c	– 525	0.01, 5.094×10^3	Mo ^{VI} , Ti ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV}
7.	V ^V , acidic medium, benzohydroxamic acid ^c	1-Hexanol, 450	0.012, 4.24×10^3	Fe ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Ti ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Mo ^{VI} , W ^{VI}
8.	V ^V , pH 5.5–8.5, 0.2%, 5,7-diiodooxine in acetone, dithionite, heating upto 60 ^{od}	Chloroform, 415	0.0067, 7.58×10^3	Fe ^{II,III}
9.	Present method	Benzene, 465	0.0049, 1.05×10^4	Pd ^{II} , Ag ^I , Mo ^{VI} > 1.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (32 more metal ions do not interfere)

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 6. ^cRef. 7. ^dRef. 8.

each); ascorbic acid (20); phosphate (10) and tartrate (5) caused <1% error. However, citrate, oxalate, fluoride and EDTA even in traces interfered seriously. Among the cations, Cd^{II} (10); Ba^{II} (7); Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mg^{II}, Sr^{II} (5 each); As^V, Al^{III} (4 each); Mn^{II}, Cu^{II} (3 each); Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, U^{VI}, Zn^{II}, Th^{IV}, Ti^{IV} (1 each); Be^{II} (0.1); Ta^V (0.07); Os^{VIII}, Ru^{III}, W^{VI}, Re^{VII} (0.05 each); Sn^{II} (0.03); Au^{III}, Pt^{IV} (0.02 each); Pd^{II}, Ag^I and Mo^{VI} (0.01 each) did not influence the absorbance. Fe^{III}, Cr^{VI}, Se^{IV}, Sb^{III}, Bi^{III}, Ir^{III} and Zr^{IV} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

Applications : The applicability of the method was tested by analysing several synthetic (some of them analogous to vicalloy, permendur, crocar and palau) and technical samples, namely high speed steel super rapid extra 500 and reverberatory flue dust with satisfactory results (Table 1). As the method did not require prior separation of iron, it was found to be superior and rapid than other methods of vanadium determination where iron interfered^{1,3}. The proposed method was found to be simple, highly reproducible and compared favourably in respect of sensitivity and selectivity with the existing ones (Table 2).

Experimental

A Shimadzu-140-02 spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used. Solutions of V^V, other ions and acetic acid were prepared as reported earlier⁴, 2'-Hydroxyacetophenonebenzoylhydrazone (HABH) (m.p. 164°) was synthesized by the literature method⁵, and dis-

solved in acetone to give 0.1% (w/v) solution. Benzene (Qualigens SQ) was distilled and the b.p. 79.5–80° fraction was used. Sodium dithionite (E. Merck, technical grade, minimum assay 85%) was used as such.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of vanadium(v) and other metal ions in suitable proportions to give various compositions. High speed steel super rapid extra 500 and reverberatory flue dust samples were brought into solution as reported⁴ and vanadium determined in the aliquots by the proposed method after adding 20 mg ascorbic acid in each case.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the sample solution containing $\leq 15 \mu\text{g}$ vanadium(v) were added sodium dithionite (250 mg), 2 M CH₃COOH (0.8 ml), 0.1% HABH (0.8 ml) followed by enough deionized water to make the final volume 10 ml. The content was heated at 50–60° for 30 s. The solution was cooled to room temperature and then equilibrated with benzene (10 ml) for 1 min. The light red organic phase was passed through Whatman filter paper (No. 41, 9 cm dia, pretreated with benzene) to remove water droplets and its absorbance measured at 465 nm against the reagent blank.

For each of 3 mg Fe^{III} and 1 mg Cr^{VI}, when present, 20 mg ascorbic acid; for 2 mg Se^{IV}, 20 mg sodium sulphite; for each of 2 mg Bi^{III} and Sb^{III}, 50 mg potassium iodide and 30 mg thiourea respectively; for 0.05 mg Zr^{IV}, 10 mg sodium phosphate and for 0.5 mg Ir^{III}, 50 mg potassium thiocyanate were added as masking agents prior to the addition of HABH in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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